

1. To what extent do you see changes necessary for the LLM tool you used to be able to adopt it into your RE processes for future projects? Please elaborate.
2. What changes to your existing processes to facilitate the adoption do you foresee?
3. What did you learn / notice while using the LLMs in the workshop that you didn't know before in the prompt engineering seminar?
4. To what extent did you change/ adapt your strategy regarding the prompt engineering techniques in the workshop based on the outputs you were getting? Please elaborate.
5. What else could've helped you prepare better to generating better-quality artefacts during the workshop in and improving your overall experience of using LLM assistance in RE? Please elaborate.